

has a very strong, unpleasant odor. Leaves developing later seldom pass through the damaged leaf base, but are malformed. In some cases, the entire tiller becomes damaged, turns dark brown, looks rotten, and has an unpleasant odor.

Disease symptoms were confined mostly to plants between tillering to boot. Seedlings that show kresiek symptoms die within a week or two; infected mature tillers do not die. In farmers' fields, almost all varieties or lines were infected, with less intensity in local varieties and higher in BR11 (see table). ■

Rice entries severely infected with kresiek at the mature plant stage in rainfed lowland fields at BRRI Regional Station, Barisal, 1990.

Designation	Infected hills (%)	Infected tillers (%)	Designation	Infected hills (%)	Infected tillers (%)
Affakilombero-1-96	90	33	BRB468-33-2-2	100	24
B5986-MR-B-1-10	100	46	BRB468-33-3-1	100	31
BR11	100	49	BRB468-33-3-2	100	24
BR23	70	36	BRB489-22-2-2	100	26
BR850-9-1-1	90	36	BRB489-51-3-2	100	27
BR1244-9-1-2-1-1	80	30	BRB489-53-1-4	100	23
BR1711-27-3-2-2	80	32	BRB489-58-2-6	90	28
BR1728-26-1-1-5	90	30	BRB489-60-1-9	90	29
BRB398-26-1-3	90	31	BRB498-6-B	100	23

Integrated pest management—insects

Influence of changing cropping pattern on insect pests of deepwater rice

Z. Islam, Entomology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Bangladesh

The traditional cropping pattern in deepwater rice (DWR) areas of Bangladesh is single DWR or mixed DWR + aus (summer rice) followed by nonrice rabi (winter) crops or fallow. During the last two decades, irrigated modern variety (MV) boro (winter rice) rice has been grown in about 0.8 million ha of the 2.0 million ha DWR area. In many DWR areas, boro - fallow or boro - rabi crops has become the dominant cropping pattern.

We compared the incidence in DWR of insect pests, particularly yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas*, in boro rice-dominant and DWR-dominant sites in central Bangladesh in early Jul 1988, when DWR was at the early elongation stage and aus rice was either at the ripening stage or harvested. YSB incidence was estimated by dissecting about 100 DWR stems from each site. Incidence of other pests was recorded.

YSB, hispa beetle *Dicladispa armigera*, and long-horned cricket *Euscyrtus concinnus* were moderate to severe at some sites (see table). In boro rice sites, stem borer (SB) damage to DWR was about six times greater than at the DWR or nonboro rice sites (see figure; $p < 0.01$, t-test on square root transformed data).

Of the 60 borer larvae and pupae found during stem dissections, 97% were YSB and the rest (3%) dark-headed borer *Chilo polychrysa*. Larvae and pupae populations were significantly higher at the boro rice sites (9.88/100 stems) than at the nonboro rice sites (0.56/100 stems, $p < 0.01$, t-test on square root transformed data). Correlation was positive between the presence of a boro crop in DWR areas and SB damage levels ($r = 0.618$, $p < 0.05$, $df = 14$).

Hispa activity was also higher in boro crop areas. Hispa incidence appeared higher in single-crop DWR fields than in mixed aus + DWR fields; the opposite was true of long-horned cricket incidence. Correlation was negative between aus +

Population densities of yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* Walker in DWR and levels of damaged stems in boro-dominant and non-boro deepwater rice locations, July 1988, Bangladesh. Boro =

Incidence of 3 insect pests in deepwater rice in selected areas in Bangladesh, 1988.^a

Location	Dominant rice crop in the area	Present rice crop	Stem borer		Hispa beetle ^b	Long-horned cricket ^b
			Damaged stems (%)	Population (no./100 stems)		
Lowhajang	DWR	DWR	0	0	M-S	Minor
Sherajdikhan	Boro	DWR	14.3	7	M-S	Minor
Mirzapur	Boro	Aus + DWR	21.9	7	Minor	M-S
Basail	DWR	Aus + DWR	1.7	0	Minor	M-S
Kalihati	DWR	Aus+DWR	1.2	0	Minor	Minor
Kalihati	Boro	DWR	2.4	1	M-S	Minor
Rupganj	Boro	DWR	2.8	2	M-S	Minor
Rupganj	DWR	DWR	0	0	Minor	Minor
Narshingdi	DWR	DWR	1.3	1	Minor	Minor
Polash	Boro	DWR	21.5	13	Minor	Minor
Arihazar	DWR	DWR	2.7	0	Minor	Minor
Dhamrai	Boro	Aus + DWR	12.5	3	Minor	M-S
Dhamrai	DWR	Aus+DWR	1.5	0	Minor	M-S
Shibalaya	DWR	Aus + DWR	11.7	3	Minor	M-S
Manikganj	DWR	Aus+DWR	3.3	1	Minor	Minor
Joydebpur	Boro	DWR	34.3	36	Minor	Minor

^aDWR = deepwater rice, aus = summer rice, boro = winter rice. ^bM-S = moderate-severe.

DWR mixed crops and hispa incidence ($r = -0.509$, $p < 0.05$, $df = 14$), but positive in the case of the long-horned cricket ($r = 0.76$, $p < 0.01$, $df = 14$).

The change in cropping pattern (increased MV boro rice cropping in DWR areas) positively influenced YSB and probably also favored hispa. Boro cropping favored the establishment of first generation YSB moths (following diapause in winter) in boro rice during Feb and Mar. Irrigated boro cropping

also reduced or eliminated high temperature stress ($>33\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) coupled with low relative humidity ($<70\%$) on the YSB during Apr-Jun, which favored population buildup.

YSB seems to concentrate in DWR following boro rice harvest. Hispa prefers young rice plants. That explains its concentration in fields with only DWR. Ripening aus rice probably influenced the high incidence of long-horned crickets in aus rice + DWR fields. ■

Dispersal range of rice insect pests under natural conditions in the Philippines

M. E. Loevinsohn, *International Development Research Centre, P.O. Box 8500, Ottawa K1G 3H9, Canada; and J. Bandong, IRRI*

We estimated the dispersal range of rice insect pests in the Philippines using a low-cost method that measures rather than manipulates natural movement. Conventional approaches (such as mark-recapture) often require handling the insects in ways that could significantly affect behavior.

During the fallow period between wet and dry season crops in early 1982, we located an isolated 1.5-ha field in Nueva Ecija where IR52 had been grown under irrigation from a shallow well pump. Except for a similar field one km west, this field had the only standing rice within several kilometers.

As the crop approached maturity, we established two parallel transects of kerosene light traps running eastward, 200 m apart. The traps were positioned within the field and at 5, 20, 50, 95, 170, 290, and 485 m into the fallow area, a geometric progression that provided greatest resolution near the field. The lamps were lit every night for more than a month, until harvest in late February.

We analyzed catches of *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *Paraponyx fluctuosalis*, and *Naranga aenescens* from 19 Jan until they began to rise after the fallow area was planted (see table). Catches of other species were too low to analyze.

The best-fitting first- or second-degree nonlinear equations are given in the table and illustrated for yellow stem borer (YSB) males in the figure. Catches declined with distance from the field. Dispersal distances were calculated from regressions corrected for background density (i.e., insects emerging from rice stubble, other host plants, and distant, scattered sources). We estimated background density from catches in four light traps at two sites 4.5 km to the east and the south. Corrected equations were integrated and rotated about the origin (in other words, assuming that movement was similar in all directions).

Toxicology of insecticides to rice leaffolder (LF) larvae

W. Tevapuchom, *Division of Entomology and Zoology, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Bangkok 10900, Thailand; and K. L. Heong, IRRI*

We evaluated the toxicology of three commonly used insecticides: an organophosphate, a carbamate, and a synthetic pyrethroid. Fourth-instar LF

Cnaphalocrocis medinalis larvae from cultures reared from moths collected in Laguna, Philippines, were topically treated at 15 d old with 0.5 μl of each insecticide solution, using an Arnold Microapplicator. Control larvae were treated with acetone.

Results are given in the table. The probit lines fitted the data well, and the insects used were found to be homogeneous.

In the test for parallelism, probit lines for BPMC and cypermethrin were found to

be parallel; diazinon significantly deviated from these two lines (see figure). The parallel lines satisfy the condition of similarity and are thus comparable.

Cypermethrin was about 250 times more toxic than BPMC. This implies that a much smaller dose of cypermethrin is required to cause LF mortality.

These results can be used as baseline data for insecticide resistance studies. ■

Probit lines of insecticides topically applied on the fourth-instar leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* larvae.

Probit analysis of diazinon, BPMC, and cypermethrin on 4th-instar larvae of rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*.

Insecticide	LC ₅₀ (ppm)	Fiducial limits (ppm)	LD ₅₀ ($\mu\text{g/larva}$)	Regression equation
Diazinon	259.8	215.5 - 310.1	0.13	$y = 5.07 + 2.70(x-12.44)$
BPMC	9896.6	6519.1 - 15264.4	4.95	$y = 4.91 + 0.95(x-13.97)$
Cypermethrin	40.6	23.0 - 141.1	0.02	$y = 4.83 + 1.11(x-11.46)$

Rice whorl maggot (RWM) incidence in Assam

M. K. Gupta, *Regional Agricultural Research Station, Assam Agricultural University, Diphu 782460, Assam, India*

In May 1990, RWM *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino was observed to attack

traditional rice variety Maibi sown 20 Mar 1990 as summer rainfed rice on a 15-20% slope in the hill district of Karbi Anglong, Assam. This is the first report of RWM attacking rice in upland fields. The insect has been recorded earlier on rice crops in the plains and low-lying areas. ■